

HIGH-PERFORMANCE WOVEN AND NON-WOVEN BALLISTIC MATERIALS FOR FLEXIBLE VESTS

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Abstract

High-performance ballistic fibers have revolutionized the flexible vests used by the military, peacekeepers and law-enforcement agencies. The beginning of this revolution was marked by the introduction of woven fabrics consisting of high tenacity nylon and aramid fibers. However, since the introduction of viscoelastic, high performance SPECTRA[®] polyethylene fibers and patented non-woven SPECTRA SHIELD[®] technology, a number of new products have been introduced for use by the ballistic vest designers.

This paper examines the comfort and ballistic performance of different types of non-woven "Shield" materials consisting of high performance SPECTRA[®] fibers, aramid fibers, and PBO fibers. A number of examples are presented which include monolithic or combination-shield products in a single vest designed to provide the optimum comfort with highest ballistic performance.

The comfort of monolithic and hybrid ballistic material configurations is discussed for a complete vest meeting the NIJ 0101.04 standards. Similarly, suggested material performance criteria are provided for selective shield systems. The guidelines include proposed number of layers and weight per unit area to meet the ballistic Resistance of a Personal Body Armor as recommended by NIJ Standard 0101.04.

The material technologies in the area of flexible ballistic vests have improved substantially in the last decade. As a result of these new technologies, military and law enforcement agencies around the world have increased protection comfort specifications, while substantially reducing the weight of the vests. The technology changes are a result of a number of factors, including the new lightweight, high-strength ballistic fibers (1), (2); the new development in the area of traditional weaving; and the technology breakthrough in the area of non-woven unidirectional ballistic composites (3).

Another factor, which has contributed to these advances, is the hybrid concept of combining more than one ballistic material in a single vest. This technique allows vest design engineers to utilize the full potential of various ballistic materials available for the flexible vests.

This paper covers the recent advances in the area of ballistics for flexible body armor which utilizes the new fibers and technologies associated with engaging maximum number of ballistic fibers, either in the area of woven or non-woven materials to the penetrating projectiles. Due to these advancements in the ballistic materials, many countries are continually upgrading their body armor performance for law-enforcement agencies and military forces. This is achieved by dropping the product specifications and adopting performance specifications to utilize the full

potential of rapidly changing ballistic technologies. The present flexible ballistic vests provide higher ballistic protection, larger body cover area, and an increased flexibility at a substantially lower weight, compared to the vests designed a few years ago.

1. BALLISTIC FIBERS

The commercial ballistic materials consist of man-made high performance ballistic fibers. Two common ballistic fibers are aramatic polyamide (aramids, commercially known under the KEVLAR® and TWARON® trademarks,) and Extended Chain Polyethylene (commercially known under the SPECTRA® and DYNEEMA® trademarks). The typical property of both types of fiber is listed in Table 1. These fibers are further processed to generate either a woven fabric roll or a non-woven unidirectional roll.

A new family of ballistic fibers has been commercialized recently. The fibers are known as PBO (poly-benzobisoxazole). The ballistic performance of this fiber shows substantial performance improvement for flexible vests.

1.1 ARAMID FIBERS

The aramid fibers are the second-generation ballistic fibers to provide higher ballistic protection compared to the ballistic nylon fibers utilized in the early 1960's.

Since the late 1980's, a number of new aramid fibers have been introduced into the ballistic market. The basic chemistry of these new and improved fibers is the same as that of the original fibers introduced in the 1960's, but these fibers have higher physical properties. The second improvement for aramid fibers is a lower denier and thinner fibers. The lower denier and improved physical properties of the fibers play an important role in defining the ballistic characteristics of a woven or non-woven unidirectional material.

1.2 EXTENDED CHAIN FIBERS

The Extended Chain Polyethylene fibers, commercially available under the SPECTRA® brand, were introduced in the mid-1980's. A unique gel spinning process produces these fibers. Due to the chemistry of these highly oriented fibers, the fibers are practically inert to a host of chemicals and moisture. The new generation of this fiber, introduced recently, has higher physical properties. The second improvement is the lower denier and thinner fibers. The ballistic property of a woven and a non-woven fabric depends on the denier of the fibers and the physical properties of the fibers.

1.3 PBO FIBERS

The PBO fibers are relatively new high-performance fibers for the ballistic vest. Although more expensive and limited in supply, the ballistic-resistant qualities of this fiber have helped set a new level of performance. The ballistic-resistance for these fibers is remarkable. At the moment, limited long-term performance data is available. A few vest companies in the United States have commercialized vests, with PBO woven fabric and Z SHIELD® ballistic material in combination with SPECTRA SHIELD® and/or GOLD FLEX® ballistic materials, and woven aramid fabrics.

2. BALLISTIC MATERIAL

A good ballistic fiber in its filament state cannot provide ballistic performance. The fibers must go through at least one additional process to manufacture a product that can engage projectiles with the fibers. The traditional process is a woven fabric where twisted fibers are partially interlocked in the weave construction.

A non-woven technology has emerged which eliminates the weaving operation. The technology is based on utilizing the full potential of ballistic fibers by eliminating the twist and kinks in the fibers associated with woven material. In this non-woven technology, two thin sets of unidirectional fiber webs are bonded in a (0, 90) configuration for engaging the projectiles.

2.1 WOVEN FABRICS

Weaving fibers into a woven fabric is a technology developed in the early stage of human civilization. However, this technology has improved with high-speed automated looms. The fiber damage in the weaving operation is minimized due to a number of modifications made at each stage where fiber is coming in contact with the loom. Despite all these advances, fibers are usually twisted and some amount of fiber is also damaged during weaving operation.

In a typical weaving operation, the fibers are twisted before weaving. The twisting of the fiber reduces fiber-to-fiber entanglement, thus maintaining the physical properties of the fibers. However, twisting also reduces the projectile engagement with individual fibers in a bundle of fiber tow.

The woven fabrics for vests (Table 2) are further processed to remove any impurity picked up as a result of the weaving operation. This process is called the “scouring” of the woven fabric. Once the fabric is scoured, a water-repellent coating may be applied. This is essential for aramid fabric so that moisture does not penetrate and reduce the ballistic resistance of the fabric.

2.2 NON-WOVEN FABRIC

The non-woven fabrics are divided into two categories: One is characterized by continuous-fiber technology and the other by chopped-fiber technology. Some of the shortcomings of the woven fabrics are eliminated in the non-woven fabrics. The main advantages are the elimination of twisting, kinks, and fiber-to-fiber rubbing. All these factors improve the ballistic performance of these materials.

2.2.1 CROSS-PLIED ROLL

In this process all the fibers are aligned parallel to each other, similar to the beaming operation in woven fabric, and then a binder or resin is applied to form into a continuous web of aligned fibers. The web holds the fiber spacing for further processing. A web of similarly aligned fibers is applied at 90-degrees to form a continuous roll. The 0-degree and 90-degree webs are further consolidated to form a unidirectional crossplied roll product. The roll product developed by this technology is a patented process; when the fiber utilized is SPECTRA[®] polyethylene fiber, this material is commercially known and available under the SPECTRA SHIELD[®] trademark (3). The SPECTRA SHIELD[®] technology is applicable to all types of continuous ballistic fibers such as ECPE fibers, aramid and PBO fibers.

2.2.1.1 GOLD FLEX® Ballistic Material

The GOLD FLEX® ballistic material is a second-generation shield, based on aramid fibers. GOLD FLEX® ballistic material offers a number of advantages over woven aramid fabric made with the identical fibers. These include thinner, substantially higher performance for a number of steel-jacketed bullets and additional flexibility to the vest (Table 5). Due to the nature of the GOLD FLEX® ballistic material, practically no stitching is required to hold the vest for multiple hits.

2.2.1.2 SPECTRA SHIELD® PLUS Ballistic Material

The SPECTRA SHIELD® PLUS family utilizes thinner, higher performance SPECTRA® fibers. It offers a number of advantages compared to the standard SPECTRA SHIELD® material. These advantages include higher ballistic resistance, thinner and more flexible material for flexible vests (Table 5).

2.2.1.3 Z SHIELD® Ballistic Material

Recently commercialized Z SHIELD® ballistic material utilizes PBO fibers in a shield configuration. As described previously, the fibers are aligned and spread into a web, coated with a binder or resin and cross-plyed to form a ballistic fabric.

The resulting product offers one of the thinnest, most flexible and high-performing ballistic materials with improved back face deformation (Table 5).

2.2.2 FELT

The high-performance fibers described for ballistic use are continuous filament fibers. These continuous ballistic fibers can be chopped into smaller fibers and randomly oriented to form an isotropic sheet of fibers. The sheet is further compacted by a set of needles. The needles push a limited amount of fibers at 90-degrees through the sheet of randomly oriented fiber felt. The felt material engages fragments much better than traditional woven fabrics do. The felts are used for fragment vests and to reduce back face deformation

3. MILITARY VESTS

The military vests are generally designed to stop either RCC fragments or FSP fragments (4) (5) (6). However, in peacekeeping missions, the military is also exposed to bullets from handguns and rifles.

The common fragments are 2 grain (gr) Right Circular Cylinder (RCC), 4 gr RCC, 16 gr RCC, 64 gr RCC and 17 gr FSP (Fragment Simulated Projectile)(4) (5). The fragments consist of hardened steel, which do not deform during penetration. The 2 gr, 4 gr, 16 gr, and 64 gr represent a broad range of fragments generated due to the explosion of artillery shells and hand grenades in the battlefield. The velocity of fragments depends upon the weight of the fragment, distance from the explosion site and the angle of the impact. The penetration mechanism of each fragment is unique. Usually it is a function of size, weight, velocity, and type of ballistic material.

The common handgun bullets are: 9 MM FMJ, 9 MM JHP, 357 Magnum, 44 Magnum, 7.62 X 25 Tokarev, .40 STW, .45 ACP, .385PECNAC, 357 SIG, 10 MM.

4. POLICE VEST

The police and law-enforcement vests are generally designed to stop low-energy bullets fired from a handgun. The vests are designed and tested as per National Institute of Justice (NIJ) protocol specified by NIJ Standard 0101.04 titled “Ballistic Resistance of Personal Body Armor” (8).

5. DESIGN OF A VEST

In designing a ballistic flexible soft vest a number of parameters are considered. These parameters are:

1. Types of projectiles: fragments (RCC or FSP) and bullets
2. Velocity of the projectiles
3. Body coverage: small, medium, and large
4. Target total weight, and weight per unit area
5. Back face deformation
6. Vest flexibility
7. Material cost

Other factors, which are considered, are the type of outer shell, straps, water-repellent treatment, stitching, and trauma pads.

The first parameter, which determines the design of the vest, is the type of projectile and the speed of each projectile listed in the specification. Based on previous flexible vest design experience or a starting guideline from the raw material supplier, a prototype shoot pack is assembled. The shoot pack is checked for areal density, layer count, and material orientation. The ballistic testing includes, V0 (stopping 100% bullet) and backface trauma as specified by NIJ (8). A few iterations changing number of layers helps to narrow down the design, and at the same time fine-tune the cost structure. A V50 test at this stage helps to assess the robustness of the design. Once the design is complete on the shoot pack, a few vests are assembled and testing is repeated to confirm the affect of the shape of the vest. If the final vest design meets the performance, body coverage area, and cost structure, vests are submitted to NIJ for certification.

The fragment vest design is almost identical to the bullet vest design for police. However, the test is conducted in the air, without a clay backing, and only V50 data is generated.

Many times a shield material is more efficient in stopping bullets, such as 9 MM FMJ, 357 Magnum, 44 Magnum (10), and steel jacked bullets. A woven fabric usually requires heavy stitching to stop these bullets and therefore reduces the flexibility and comfort of the vest. The fragment vest is commonly made out of woven fabrics and requires relatively less stitching.

6. CONCLUSION

Due to technology advancement in the area of fibers and ballistic materials, the military and law-enforcement agencies have higher ballistic protection and lower-weight armor for high mobility. The present armor systems:

1. Are thinner and less bulky
2. Are much lighter in weight
3. Are less stiff and more flexible in vests
4. Provide higher body coverage
5. Protect from multiple threats
6. Are better at protecting against multiple angle shots
7. Defeat both fragments and bullet resistance

7. REFERENCES

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3. Shield Patent, e.g., US 4,916,000
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TABLE 1

Properties of Ballistic Fibers

	SPECTRA®		ARAMID		PBO	
	S-900	S-1000	LM	HM	AS	HM
Tenacity, G/D	30	35	22	22	42	42
Modulus, G/D	1400	2000	488	976	1300	2000
Elongation, %	3.5	2.7	3.6	2.8	3.5	2.5

TABLE 2

Typical Fabric Styles for Ballistic Vest

	STYLE	DENIER	WEAVE	WEIGHT (Oz/ sq. yd)
SPECTRA® Fibers	960	375	32 X 32	2.5
	955	215	56 X 56	3.2
	945	215	45 X 45	2.6
Aramid fibers	704	840	31 X 31	6.5
	8431	840	31 X 31	6.5
	705	850	31 X 31	6.8
	706	600	34 X 34	5.3

TABLE 3*SPECTRA SHIELD*[®] Non-Woven Ballistic Materials

MATERIAL	THICKNESS (mm)	WEIGHT (oz/ sq. yd)
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> [®]		
LCR	0.18	4.6
FLEX	0.18	4.4
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> [®] PLUS		
LCR	0.13	3.3
FLEX	0.13	3.3
<i>GOLD FLEX</i> [®]	0.30	6.8
<i>Z SHIELD</i> [®]	0.08	2.9

TABLE 4

Hybrid Military Vests

FRAGMENT (RCC)

	2 gr	4 gr	16 gr	64 gr
V50 (fps), 0 deg	2530	2240	1900	1575
V50(fps), 45 deg	2730	2730	1970	1660

HANDGUN

9 MM,124 gr, FMJ	V50 (fps)	V 0 (fps)	Deformation(in)
Required	1525	1400	1.73
Desired	1625	1500	1.73

Vest Material 1: *SPECTRA*[®] fiber-containing fabric Style 945 and *GOLD FLEX*[®], Areal Density 0.96 psf

Vest Material 2: *SPECTRA*[®] fiber-containing fabric Style 945 and aramid woven fabric

TABLE 5

Suggested starting point for monolithic vest to meet NIJ 0101.04, Level IIIA

Material	Areal Density (psf)
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ®	1.20+/-0.05
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® PLUS	1.10+/-0.05
GOLD FLEX®	1.15+/- 0.05
Z SHIELD®	0.70+/-0.05